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Theoretical Control Dynamics for Error Detection in EDA with Touch Screen Using Moisture Detection on Fingerprint

Fatima Isiaka

Department of Computer Science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This paper investigates the dynamic control for error detection on physiological response using a touch screen that measures the electrodermal activity (EDA) of forty participants aged between 30 – 42, their EDA (Skin conductance response (SCR)) was recorded based on a non-invasive method by placing fingertips on the touch screen with conductance that detects moisture content and reaction to basic stimuli. A dynamic control model of order three was used with a control evaluator that reads the image and uses the motion detection principles to capture the input matrix of data made by fingerprint. The input parameter is simulated with time similar to the initial moisture content present on the fingertips of the participants. The impact of a fingerprint with moisture present is simulated with the EDA and Temperature. The control evaluator also generates an error in performance for the EDA readings using a schematic sequence which is typical of all control dynamics that uses space space-identified model (N4Sid) with a third-order differential equation. The result shows zero error for physiological parameters used and an absolute -0.6% on moisture content on skin based on an aggregate of the participants' demographic data.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This paper introduces a novel non-invasive and unobtrusive touch screen sensor for monitoring the response output based on the moisture content of fingertips for electrodermal activity reading that could also be used in health-related computing systems. The paper briefly introduces the description of touch screen devices capable of acquiring the EDA of respondents to detect their relaxation and stress conditions from the acquired physiological signals. The participants were asked to place their fingertips on the user-friendly device to allow a continuous physiological measurement to be taken. This is done to validate the error and accurate operation of the touch sensor mechanism for EDA reading.

Most international affective picture systems are used to control experiments involving a lot of participants and collected signals are processed with features extracted based on statistical analysis. This analysis is mostly based on the calm and distressed mood classification of the readings, some of the results show that these devices are solely based on EDA signal processing reports and have a high performance of above 89% inaccuracy when distinguishing calm conditions from distressed conditions. This paper introduces a control evaluation that captures the image of the skin with moisture reads the continuous reaction from the surface of the touch device and computes errors for each user's physiological attributes.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Some research work on the importance of using EDA to validate the correction of operation of wearable EDA devices, pictures from both local and international affective picture system that uses a control experiment involving participants [20, 24, 8, 4, 18, 1, 23, 11, 12, 13]. The collected signals are then processed, and features and basic attributes are extracted which are statistically analysed to perform the classification between relaxed and stressed cognitive responses of the participants. The results show that these wearable devices have high accuracy and can be distinguished by classifying the calm and distressed states of the users. Other research [16, 30, 3, 7, 22, 9, 6, 29] has applied touch sensors to detect dryness and wetness of fingers and their impact on the biometric performance and the measurement of the skin characteristics for actionable quality, they collected ground truth fingerprint skin moisture dataset containing 6600 samples from several 33 subjects using five different optical sensors, two of these claimed to work well in extreme skin moisture conditions while controlling conditions apply cream and water to perform objective measurements of skin moisture before each fingerprint capture.

The analysis shows the relationship between measured moisture and biometric performance across the five sensors and comparison scores from three of the commercial providers confirm the claim that resistance to excessive moisture is valid. The result also indicates that the sensor resistant to excessive moisture performance is worse on dry fingerprints than the sensor not resistant to excessive moisture. Some research [10, 5, 31, 17, 15, 26, 2, 14, 27, 28, 25] has also presented a rear-projected multi-touch table that identified users biometrically based on their fingerprints during each touch interaction. The project accomplishes its procedures by a new type of screen material which includes a large fibre optic plate and this plate diffuses light on transmission thereby allowing it to act as a projected surface. The plate also reflects light secularly, which produces the contrast required for fingerprint sensing. The project is the first interactive tabletop system that authenticates users during touch interaction based on a non-obtrusive method and can securely be used as a biometric feature for fingerprints [21, 19].

3 METHOD

The method used in this paper is based on a touch screen concept from the Microsoft Operating system (OS) Tablet that reads input of the fingertips based on a schematic module used in detecting moisture content (Figure 1) that derives a continuous reading simulated with time to the control evaluator using control dynamics (Equation 1). Matlab was used to connect the screen port and the resultant input is the matrix X containing an amount of moisture content contained on the fingertips at a certain initial stage of the contact point. The fingertip image is captured from the touch screen and the changes in the electrostatic field are registered on the inner image capture lens, this registers a continuous touch screen that is evaluated by the image evaluator. The controller evaluator outputs the detected image matrix of moisture content on the fingertip which is then continuously simulated and equivalent to the EDA of the skin. This is usually based on the electrical changes on the skin caused by sweat on the sweat gland while the user is involved in a complex program on the interface. Normally some skin is found to be dehydrated but the application of moisturiser can induce a slight response and active reaction mood in response to stimuli.

Forty participants were recruited to take part in the experiment, each asked to place their fingertips on the touch screen of the tablet, and each impact was simulated in a continuous reading based on a third-order differential equation. The aggregate from the participant's response data is computed and used as an exemplary data analysis on the controller evaluator. A controller evaluator is a form of intelligent analytics that registers response values and reading that detects baseline to distinguish them from the tonic and phasic changes of the physiological response.

4 RESULT

Figure 2 shows the aggregate of the resultant response of the participants, high phasic change can correspond to optimal peaks and this example shows a response peak at $5.0\mu s$ which indicates a significant response state of the

Figure 1: Schematic representation of EDA response signal propagation from the touch screen sensor on the tablet

participants, the input value of moisture content is noisy at the initial stage, and the application of a moving average filter smoothens the readings to a clear EDA signal, the baseline is used to detect all phasic changes and its equivalent user stimulus interface correlates. The Skin temperature (ST) is a measure based on $(30 \times X oC)$, where X represents the input EDA value at the initial stage. The latency for all physiological responses is detected based on the hand-clap method from stimulus onset and this is used to measure and detect phasic changes to its user-interface correlates.

Figure 2: Aggregate response signal of participants with detected SCR, moisture, and ST with computed baseline.

The physiological parameters (Moisture content, SCR, ST, MappedFY, and MappedFX) are the user attributes that serve as the input to the control dynamics (Figure 3). Each attribute contributes significantly to the model prediction performance with zero error entries detected, and acceptance of the moisture content (absolute -0.64%). This shows that each of these attributes supports extensively the model performance. The control dynamics for the

dynamic changes in physiological response can produce response states that represent the mechanism in the sympathetic nervous system (SNS) as a form of a physiological control system for simulation of the cognitive response of users to visual stimuli this is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^3 X}{dy^3} &= Au(t) + Bu(t) + Cu(t); \\ y &= Du(t) + Eu(t) + Fu(t); \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where the free parameters A, B, C, D , and E are input matrices that hold the performance value of the user attributes, X, t and u are the metrics representing the input image or detected moisture content, the rate of change with time and input matrix, F is the resultant matrix for the output variables, while y is response output, usually the vector-matrix that represents the response states of the resultant signal.

Figure 3: Residual output from performance metrics of the dynamic control system (controller evaluator).

5 CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates the concept in theoretical control dynamics for error detection in electrodermal activity with a touch screen using moisture detection on fingerprint, a control system model was used as a control evaluator that reads in the image and uses the motion detection principles to capture input matrix of data made by fingerprint. The input parameter is simulated with time similar to the initial moisture content present in the palms of the participants during the experiment session. The impact of the fingerprint with the moisture contained in it is simulated with the EDA and Temperature. The control evaluator also generates an error in performance for the EDA readings using a scheming sequence that is typical of all control dynamics that uses space space-identified model (N4Sid) with a fourth-order differential equation. The result shows zero error for physiological parameters used and an absolute -0.6% on moisture content on the skin based on an aggregate of the participants' demographic data. The results also pave the way for further investigations on how this can affect the data model with other standard neural inference machines like the auto-encoders and convolutional neural network (CNN) for an advanced model built for state-of-the-art mechanisms on robotics and mechanical systems.

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